

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Rethinking Alternatives to Migrant Returns: Comparative Insights from Greece, Germany, and Turkey and the Human Rights Trade-Offs

Concept Note

Authors:

N. Ela GÖKALP ARAS and Neva Övünç ÖZTÜRK

Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul, SRII

D9.1–January 2026

Co-funded by

Canada Excellence
Research Chair in
Migration & Integration

Deliverable Information

Project acronym	Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond
Project no.	101094341
WP	9
Deliverable title	Concept Note - “Rethinking Alternatives to Migrant Returns: Comparative Insights from Greece, Germany, and Turkey and the Human Rights Trade-Offs”
Deliverable type	R – Document, report
Version	V1
Date	January 2026
Responsible partners	Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul (SRII)
Authors	N. E. Gökalp Aras and N. Ö. Öztürk
Dissemination level	Public

Revision History

Version	Date	Authors	Changes
V1	09.11.2025	N. Ela Gökalp Aras, Neva Ö. Öztürk	The first draft was submitted to the WP9 co-leaders, the EKKE, and the BICC teams for the selected Greece and Germany cases.
V2	07.01.2026	N. Ela Gökalp Aras, Neva Ö. Öztürk	Final version submitted.

© SRII

This research was conducted under the Horizon Europe project “GAPS: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond” (101094341). The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to the author at ela.gokalparas@sri.org.tr; neva.ozturk@sri.org.tr

Cite as:

Gökalp Aras, N. E. and Öztürk, N. Ö (2026). “Rethinking Alternatives to Migrant Returns: Comparative Insights from Greece, Germany, and Turkey and the Human Rights Trade-Offs”, in *GAPs Working paper 2026/04*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18181159

1. Introduction

In recent years, the governance of migration has increasingly centred around return policies as the cornerstone of migration management. There is as a shift in asylum and migration policies towards promoting or facilitating the return of migrants and refugees to their home countries, rather than long-term settlement, as called “return turn” that involves measures like granting temporary protection permits, stricter permanent residency requirements, and increased efforts to cease refugee status for those whose need for protection is deemed no longer to exist (Schultz, 2020; King & Kuschminder, 2022; Stel, 2025). Despite actual return rates remaining low, this return trend is associated with the growing policy emphasis on deportations, readmission agreements, and voluntary return mechanisms. According to Eurostat (2025), the number of non-EU citizens who received an order to leave the EU remains consistently high, fluctuating roughly between 105,000 and 125,000 persons per quarter. However, the number of people who were actually returned to a third country following an order to leave generally remained between 20,000 and 35,000. Even in quarters with higher return rates, such as Q4 2024 and Q1 2025, the gap between those ordered to leave and those who were effectively returned remains very large. In other words, while the EU issues a high volume of return orders, only a relatively small share of these orders results in actual removals, showing once again the persistent implementation gap regarding the return rate, the gap between ‘return decisions’ and ‘returns carried out’ (Ibid.) Against this backdrop, policymakers, scholars, and international organisations have begun to explore alternatives to migrant return (ATR) as potential pathways to reconcile control objectives with human rights obligations and practical constraints. ATR policies are defined as “all implicit and explicit policies implemented in receiving countries for those who cannot be easily returned” (Gül Ince-Beqo et al., 2024: 9).

While return has become a central policy priority, the dominant literature and policy discourse remain highly skewed toward return enforcement, deportation capacity, readmission agreements, operational barriers, and ‘return effectiveness’ metrics that mainly focuses on the return rates, rather than toward those governance instruments that actually structure the vast majority of non-removals (Guild et al., 2017; Carrera and Geddes, 2021). Thus, policy attention is primarily directed at the minority of cases where return is executed, while the everyday government of the deportable majority, those who remain on European territory despite removal orders, remains under-theorised and analytically fragmented. ATR, therefore, matters because it is not a marginal exception but the de facto core of return governance practice: it manages non-return, prolongs deportability, and distributes rights in incremental, conditional, and unequal ways. Moreover, although ATR are often normatively presented as “humane”, “rights-sensitive” or “pragmatic” solutions, there is a lack of conceptual clarity on what counts as an ATR, what differentiates ATR from alternatives to detention, and how rights are structured and restricted within these modalities. This conceptual gap has produced a situation in which ATR instruments are frequently implemented in policy but poorly theorised in research.

Although the GAPs project as a whole is centred on return governance, this does not mean that removal itself is the empirical centre of gravity. On the contrary, the GAPs Project’s different work packages show that most return systems do not result in enforced removal, but rather in long-term non-return situations. It is precisely for this reason that the Project’s Work Package 9 (WP9) concentrates on alternatives to return. WP9 takes the GAPs’ return focus seriously, but follows its internal logic to the next analytical step: if return is the normative policy horizon, yet non-return is the empirical reality, then ATRs are not peripheral but structurally central. In this sense, the WP9 perspective complements the other work packages; rather than analysing return enforcement alone, it examines how deportability is governed when return does not occur, and how rights are allocated, suspended, or conditioned in those non-removal arrangements. In this regard, this concept note advances ATR as a legitimate, autonomous field of analysis rather than a residual category alongside detention or deportation, and argues that systematic attention to the human rights trade-offs within ATR is necessary to understand

contemporary return governance in practice. This conceptualisation directly supports a human-rights trade-off analysis by exposing how policies presented as humanitarian or voluntary may, in practice, sustain coercive pressures and unequal access to rights. To analyse ATR is critical because while “alternatives” are often framed as humane and pragmatic measures, they are neither uniform nor free from coercive or disciplinary dimensions. ATR have expanded in scope as states seek compliance and control without, or prior to, forced removal. Therefore, our contribution is to foreground these human rights trade-offs as an explicit analytical lens.

However, before turning to the limitations and human-rights concerns associated with ATRs, it is important to acknowledge the positive rationales that have motivated their introduction in several migration regimes. In principle, ATRs can contribute to reducing the harms associated with detention and forced removal, offering states more proportionate and cost-effective tools to manage non-removability (FRA, 2015; EUAA, 2024). They are also frequently presented as mechanisms that enhance migrants’ social stability by allowing access, however partial, to employment, education, or basic services, thereby mitigating the vulnerability and irregularity that prolonged enforcement gaps often produce (Kraler, 2019; PICUM, 2022). Moreover, ATRs may serve pragmatic state interests by supporting labour market needs, facilitating administrative planning, and promoting compliance through incentives rather than coercion (Eule et al., 2019). Under these conditions, ATRs are normatively framed as humane, pragmatic, and mutually beneficial instruments capable of reconciling migration control with fundamental rights obligations. However, as our analysis demonstrates, the actual design and implementation of ATRs frequently depart from these ideals, resulting in significant human rights trade-offs that must be carefully scrutinised.

In this framework, this concept note asks: How are ATRs designed and deployed across different governance contexts, and what human rights trade-offs do they entail for deportable irregular migrants? In light of this research question, this concept paper develops a comparative framework for analysing existing alternatives to return across three country cases: Greece, Germany, and Turkey. These cases represent distinct governance logics and legal traditions. Greece’s employment-based regularisation approach, Germany’s administrative toleration model (*Duldung*), and Turkey’s hybrid regime, which combines temporary protection and voluntary return under externalised EU influence, illustrate three distinct logics of governing “deportable” irregularity. These cases enable us to analyse ATR at the EU’s external frontier, within the EU’s administrative core, and in the externalised periphery.

In selecting Greece, Germany and Turkey, we follow the internal rationale already established within the GAPs Consortium regarding the three principal modalities through which alternatives to return are operationalised. At the same time, this tripartite structuring resonates with the broader European policy-research field: the FAIR report on “Legitimate Return and Alternatives to Return” similarly identifies a three-fold differentiation between explicit, semi-explicit and implicit forms of non-removal (FAIR Report, 2024). Greece, Germany, and Turkey, therefore, do not merely represent convenient or familiar cases, but are chosen because they empirically exemplify each of these three ideal types. Greece corresponds to the explicit, employment-linked regularisation model; Germany to semi-explicit administrative toleration (*Duldung*); and Turkey represents the third type, as non-removal in Turkey is not organised through codified regularisation mechanisms but rather through temporary, discretionary, and externally influenced protection regimes that suspend deportability rather than extinguish it. This alignment enables us to focus our analysis on deportable irregular migrants, those who are legally subject to removal, even where return cannot be carried out in practice, and who therefore constitute the primary subjects of ATR instruments. It facilitates a systematic assessment of human rights trade-offs across distinct ATR logics. A more detailed conceptual elaboration of this three-part schema will be presented in the analysis’s conceptual section. However, it should be noted that, while Germany’s

temporary protection for Ukrainians and Turkey’s temporary protection regime for Syrians may appear similar at first glance, this concept note argues that Turkey represents a distinct alternative to return. The distinction does not lie in the mere existence of temporary protection, but in how non-removal is governed. In Germany, temporary protection operates within a rights-based EU legal framework that explicitly suspends deportability and provides a pathway towards secure residence.

In contrast, Turkey’s non-removal regime is characterised by executive discretion, prolonged temporariness, fragmented legal statuses, and the systematic preservation of deportability. Temporary protection in Turkey functions not as a bridge to legal inclusion, but as a mechanism of managed non-return embedded in externalised return governance. This makes Turkey analytically distinct from EU-based protection regimes and justifies its classification as an implicit or hybrid alternative to return. Turkey’s implicit ATR regime cannot be understood without reference to EU externalisation. However, externalisation functions here as a driver of non-removal governance rather than as a defining typological feature. The distinctiveness of the Turkish case lies in how temporality, discretion, and legal fragmentation structure everyday non-removal. The concept note proceeds in four analytical steps. First, we outline the conceptual framework that underpins our understanding of ATR as a governance instrument situated within the coercive architecture of deportability. Second, we examine ATR empirically through three selected country cases—Greece, Germany, and Turkey—which collectively represent the three principal ATR modalities (explicit, semi-explicit, and implicit) identified in both the GAPs’ internal conceptual work and the FAIR “legitimate return and alternatives” report. Third, we conduct a human rights trade-off analysis that evaluates how these alternative modalities shape the rights, vulnerabilities, and lived conditions of deportable irregular migrants, rather than assuming that ATR are inherently protective or benign. The concept note closes with a discussion and conclusion that synthesises the comparative insights and reflects on the implications for future empirical research and for the normative evaluation of ATR within contemporary return governance.

2. Conceptual Framework: Defining Alternatives to Return

Within the GAPs Project¹, return is conceptualised as a field of power and negotiation, shaped by barriers to cooperation, the politics of removability, and the gap between what states intend and what actually happens, rather than as a simple administrative endpoint (Şahin Mencütek et al., 2023). Therefore, this concept note also approaches return through the lens of coerced return, as this is the space where the state’s power over deportable irregular migrants becomes most visible. This is also where the GAPs Project explicitly converges with the FAiR Project, which conceptualises ‘return’ as a question of legitimacy in situations where voluntariness is eroded or collapsed (Gül Ince-Beqo et al., 2024: 9). The GAPs positions coerced return as a governance modality in which deportability is operationalised even when removal does not physically occur. In both approaches, return is not merely an administrative event but a coercion-legitimacy problem centred on the management of those who can, in principle, be removed, in other words, the deportable. Therefore, this concept note recognises that the actual deployment of ATR instruments in practice is overwhelmingly directed at deportable irregular migrants, those who are legally and practically removable and thus embedded within the coercive return continuum. Therefore, in practice, alternatives to return instruments are specifically targeted at those who are deportable, for whom removal is both legally and practically possible. This approach is also adopted by the FAiR Project’s² “Legitimate return and Alternatives to Return” paper (Torres Chedraui et al., 2024), where alternatives to return are operationalised as internal control tools for deportable subjects, including detention pending deportation, mobility restrictions, exclusion from welfare, and the obligation to reside

¹ Further information and the publications are available at <https://www.returnmigration.eu/>

² GAPs Project works closely with other Horizon Europe projects working on return migration and conditions of irregular migrants such as Finding Agreement in Return (FAIR) Project. Further infd the publications are available at: <https://fair-return.org/the-team/v>

in return centres, which is observed and found in Greece during the GAPs' Project research. However, that point required further discussion since conceptually, ATRs are primarily designed for deportable persons, that is, individuals who are legally subject to removal but who cannot be returned in practice due to legal, political, or operational constraints. This is because the very notion of an "alternative to return" presupposes the legal possibility of return: where removal is legally excluded, for instance due to the principle of non-refoulement, return is no longer an available policy option and therefore cannot meaningfully be substituted by an "alternative". In this sense, ATRs are analytically anchored in the governance of deportability rather than in the protection of non-removable persons.

However, empirical evidence across different migration regimes demonstrates that ATR instruments are frequently applied beyond this conceptual core. In practice, legally non-deportable persons are often governed through ATR-like arrangements that prolong temporality, impose conditional access to rights, and preserve uncertainty regarding future legal status. Temporary protection regimes, humanitarian residence permits, or prolonged toleration statuses may formally suspend removal, yet they often maintain the underlying logic of deportability by keeping return as a latent and politically reactivatable horizon. This extension of ATR mechanisms to non-deportable populations constitutes a structural tension rather than a conceptual inconsistency. It reflects the fact that contemporary return governance increasingly operates through graduated coercion and temporal management rather than through clear legal dichotomies between removability and protection. As a result, the boundary between deportable and non-deportable status becomes blurred in practice, even when it remains formally intact in law. From an analytical perspective, this blurring is not accidental but indicative of how states govern non-return through uncertainty, conditionality, and the strategic use of temporality.

Accordingly, this concept note treats alternatives to return as governance instruments primarily oriented toward deportable persons, while critically examining how their deployment in practice often extends to legally non-deportable groups. This empirical overlap is approached not as a definitional flaw of the ATR concept, but as a key site of human-rights trade-offs, where protection is reframed as a form of managed non-removal and where prolonged liminality itself may become a source of coercive pressure. Therefore, our analytical starting point is deportable irregular migrants, not because non-deportable individuals are irrelevant, but because the coercive and disciplinary logic of ATR operates most clearly in relation to deportable irregularity.

However, this concept note also approaches ATR not as an isolated policy set, but rather as part of the same governance field, where measures may modulate, delay, reframe, or, in some cases, transform removal. While several ATR modalities operate by managing deportability through temporality and conditionality, others, most notably regularisation pathways, function as rights-oriented alternatives that explicitly aim to reduce or extinguish deportability through legal status conversion. Accordingly, ATR should not be understood as a single coercive mechanism, but as a spectrum ranging from rights-oriented, inclusionary pathways to temporality-based, non-removal arrangements. Within this spectrum, we analytically distinguish between rights-oriented ATRs, such as explicit regularisation pathways that convert status and stabilise residence, and control-oriented ATRs, which manage non-removal through temporariness, conditionality, and graduated coercion. In this sense, ATRs are embedded as graduated coercion that includes temporary protection, toleration, or limited legal statuses, allowing for residence without full regularisation, reflecting a shift from outright removal to managed non-return. Although ATRs are often presented normatively as "humane solutions" distinct from enforcement, empirical work shows that they often operate as instruments of graduated coercion rather than genuine protective alternatives.

Instead of deploying direct force, states use ATR to gradually narrow the life-chances of deportable irregular migrants by linking access to rights, mobility, welfare, or documentation to behavioural compliance with return pathways. In this sense, ATR does not stand outside the deportation apparatus; it is part of a continuum in which pressure increases incrementally rather than through a single decisive coercive act (Eule et al., 2019; Tazzioli, 2020a). Thus, we argue that ATR often functions less as an alternative to return than as a mechanism that manages deportability and extends enforcement logics over time in relation to graduated coercion. However, from a policy and governance perspective, this analysis does not suggest abandoning alternatives to return, but instead redefining their normative orientation. A rights-consistent alternative to return would need to move beyond temporality and conditionality as default governing tools. Instead, ATR should be designed as predictable and rights-oriented pathways that progressively reduce deportability rather than merely managing it. This implies three minimum requirements: first, legal clarity and temporal proportionality, ensuring that temporary measures do not become indefinite forms of liminality; second, access to substantive rights independent of behavioural conditionality or return compliance; and third, the existence of clear transition pathways toward more secure legal status, including regularisation, where return is not feasible in the medium term. Such an approach would allow ATR to function as a genuine alternative to return, rather than as instruments of deferred enforcement, while remaining compatible with states' regulatory interests. We therefore propose understanding rights-oriented ATR as a distinct category within the broader ATR spectrum, encompassing regularisation pathways and other durable status solutions that aim to extinguish deportability rather than prolong it.

Graduated coercion (Eule et al., 2019) offers a conceptual bridge for us, as it reflects our findings from the GAPs Project regarding coerced returns and helps us understand why ATR should not be read as inherently benign alternatives to deportation, but rather as governance modalities that manage deportability in different ways. While some ATRs, particularly rights-oriented pathways such as employment- or training-based toleration, may stabilise stay and facilitate long-term residence, others operate through temporality, conditionality, and uncertainty, thereby sustaining the underlying logic of deportability even in the absence of immediate removal. Empirically, this diversity of outcomes is particularly visible in Germany, where *Duldung* has often functioned as a long-term stabilising status and, in many cases, as a pathway to residence rather than as a precursor to deportation. However, the presence of stabilising outcomes does not negate the fact that deportability formally remains in place and that access to rights and security is conditioned, selective, and reversible. In this perspective, the absence of physical removal does not imply the absence of coercion; instead, coercion is exercised through conditional access to rights, reporting duties, labour-market conditionality, and time-limited legal insecurity, forms of pressure that steer behaviour without resorting to force. This is the case for all the selected country-cases, particularly Greece and Turkey. ATR thus constitutes structured non-removal within a coercive architecture, in which deportability remains legally intact and is used as leverage rather than executed. In other words, ATRs are not external to return enforcement, but embedded in the same continuum of graduated coercion that organises the “management of the deportable” (Ibid.).

In light of this background, it is a fact that the notion of ATR lacks a unified conceptual definition, often overlapping with related terms such as alternatives to detention (ATD), toleration statuses, and voluntary return programmes (FRA, 2015; UNHCR and IOM, 2018; Llynn, 2019; EUAA, 2024; GDP, 2025). Conceptually, ATR refers to any legal, administrative, or social mechanism allowing individuals who are otherwise subject to return to remain in the host state, temporarily or permanently, under specified conditions. The FAiR Project defines it as “All implicit and explicit policies implemented in receiving countries for those who cannot be easily returned.” (Ince-Beqo et al., 2024, p. 9).

Three key features that define ATR in contemporary migration governance can be summarised as legal and administrative temporality, governance through uncertainty, and humanitarian

rationalisation of control. For this concept note, we adopt the FAiR Project’s categorisation (Torres Chedraui et al., 2024), and we approach ATR as a spectrum structured by (i) the degree of legal codification and (ii) whether non-removal is the intended outcome. In this framework, we follow the FAiR’s threefold typology:

1. **Explicit ATR (law-based inclusion):** regularisation through employment (mainly in Southern European countries for the labour-market needs) or humanitarian grounds (mainly in Northern European countries for the rejected asylum seekers), long residence/integration, and humanitarian/family/medical titles where the stated aim is continued stay (Kraler, 2019; PICUM, 2022; Torres Chedraui et al., 2024). Humanitarian grounds are widely used in the Greek case too; actually, it was the only way to regularisation during the last decades, based on the previous legislation, which is now terminated. The FAiR Projects defines “regularisation as an act of legal integration through which irregular migrants are included in mainstream social and legal structures by means of a legal status” (Kraler 2019, cited in Torres Chedraui et al., 2024, p. 15). The two common ways to grant legal status to irregular migrants are: time-limited programmes, which involve large numbers of applicants at once and open-ended procedures aimed at individual cases, with more administrative discretion and typically involving fewer people (Ibid.).
2. **Semi-explicit ATR (structured non-removal):** Regularisation pathways are not explicitly defined, but based on some grey areas between regularity and irregularity, without protection from deportation and without access to services in some cases (Ibid., p. 16). It is briefly codified toleration/suspension regimes, along with selective transition channels, that stabilise presence without branding it as regularisation (Eule et al., 2019; BAMF, 2023). In this category, also official toleration is visible, in particular for the rejected asylum seekers who cannot currently be deported can be the subject of this ATR, which is not a residence permit and does not eliminate deportability with limited access to some rights such as employment but still as remaining at the bottom of the civic hierarchy (Torres Chedraui et al., 2024, p. 16).
3. **Implicit ATR (tacit non-enforcement):** It refers to de facto non-removal produced by informal-economy reliance, administrative inaction, or selective enforcement, where deportability is maintained symbolically but not exercised at scale (Ibid., pp. 16-17). In this model, irregularity does not always lead to regularisation or a return. It may occur irregularly, sometimes for extended periods (Ibid.). This also resembles the Greek and Turkish cases. There are different strategies for this type of ATR: “Informal economy, informal tolerance and selectivity; institutional abandonment and solidarity networks; detention and transit to other countries” (Ibid.). For this type, states are highly selective, and stratification is based mainly on nationality, country of origin, and legal status. While not all unauthorised immigrants are treated equally before the law, they are granted different legal statuses and subject to varying implementations and procedures, such as Syrians under Temporary Protection (SuTP) and Afghans in Turkey (Gökalp Aras et al., 2025a).

Table 1 summarises the three principal modalities of ATR, as used in this concept note. Each row represents a distinct governance logic through which states manage the presence of deportable irregular migrants in situations where removal does not occur. The first model captures explicit regularisation, where non-removal is organised through employment-linked status conversion (for example, labour-based regularisation decrees). The second model describes semi-explicit administrative toleration, in which migrants are not returned and are issued tolerated-stay statuses, but are not granted residence rights. The third model refers to implicit or hybrid non-removal, in which non-return is achieved through temporary protection, EU externalisation arrangements, and fragmented rights frameworks rather than direct regularisation. Together, the three rows show that ATR is not a single instrument but a spectrum of state practices that maintain deportability while, in different ways, postpone, reframe, or manage return.

Table 1: Three ATR modalities³, with a third category broadened for implicit/hybrid forms

ATR modality	Core mechanism	Visibility / Legal status	State logic of use	Typical governance tools	How deportability is treated
1) Explicit alternatives (employment or humanitarian reasons linked)	Periodic, codified regularisation measures tied to labour market participation or economic need	<i>visible</i> and legislated, but not continuous/not rights-based ⁴	pragmatic absorption of irregular workers when removal is not feasible	labour-based status conversion; exceptional decrees; temporary residence	deportability softened in exchange for labour utility; can be reactivated
2) Semi-alternatives (Quota decrees and toleration status)	Legally defined “tolerated stay” (e.g. Duldung-type) plus narrow conditional pathways from toleration to temporary residence	visible in law, but formal residence withheld; thresholds conditionality	rule-bound <i>graduated inclusion</i> from non-removal → time-limited residence	tolerated stay, vocational training toleration, employment toleration, 5-year “opportunity” tracks	deportability retained as a legal basis; conversion is conditional and reversible
3) Implicit/hybrid non-removal under protection+ externalisation	Non-deportability through temporary protection, partial social rights, and EU externalisation arrangements instruments	low visibility / fragmented; status regimes partially defined through <i>protection</i> , not through “ATR” language	managing non-return via temporary inclusion, protection categories, and externalised return partnerships	temporary protection cards, humanitarian clauses, “voluntary return” framed within EU conditionality, mobility management centres	deportability symbolically affirmed but practically deferred; non-removal governed through temporality and fragmentation rather than legal status conversion

3. Methodological Approach

This paper adopts a comparative qualitative framework to map and analyse ATR practices in three distinct national contexts: Greece, Germany, and Turkey. The comparative logic is based on the most-different systems design, in which the selected cases differ in structure but address similar challenges in return enforcement and migrant management.

The first part of the note relies primarily on desk research and secondary sources. We draw from peer-reviewed scholarship, country dossiers, international reports, and EU policy

³ Adapted from the FaiR Project (Torres Chedraui et al., 2024).

⁴ Humanitarian grounds and employment-based protections are, in principle, rights-based and inclusionary. The problem, however, lies not in these protections themselves, but in their increasing translation into temporary, renewable, and conditional statuses, which reintroduce uncertainty and limit their capacity to function as durable alternatives to return.

documents, rather than generating new primary data. The analysis is qualitative in nature, as its objective is to interpret policy instruments and discursive framings, rather than to measure outcomes statistically. Methodologically, we use comparative analysis, reading each country case (Greece, Germany, and Turkey) not as “case studies” in the narrow sense, but as empirical modalities of ATR. By “empirical modalities”, we mean analytically distinct configurations of ATR governance rather than comprehensive national case studies, allowing comparison of how different legal and administrative logics structure non-removal. This comparative reading enables us to identify differences in rationalities (labour-based regularisation; administrative toleration; temporality/externalisation) rather than to compare country “performance”. In this sense, comparison is used to differentiate analytically between distinct ATR governance logics, rather than to benchmark countries on policy effectiveness or outcomes. In this framework, the majority of the secondary data is derived from the GAPs Project reports and secondary sources, the FAiR Project’s publications, and other legislative texts, policy papers, and academic literature. The analysis focuses on the legal and institutional design of the alternatives.

Our methodological approach explicitly foregrounds the normative human-rights implications of ATR and subjects them to systematic assessment. The adopted human rights trade-off analysis is conducted as a normative-legal assessment rather than a quantitative rights-ranking exercise. Methodologically, the starting point is that ATR should be evaluated against international human rights law standards that are binding regardless of immigration status. We therefore examine the extent to which each ATR modality (semi-explicit employment-linked, semi-explicit administrative toleration, implicit/hybrid temporary protection) affects key legal entitlements and legal security for deportable persons. In other words, the trade-off is not measured by whether a return occurs, but by how far each alternative respects, restricts, or conditions rights recognised in international human rights law.

The legal analysis therefore focuses on three legal dimensions: (1) the degree of legal certainty and clarity of status; (2) the content of the rights attached to that status (e.g. access to health, labour market, education); and (3) the degree to which the possibility of return (deportability). Each ATR modality is therefore assessed as a ‘legal instrument of non-removal’ or in the light of the ‘non-refoulement principle’, where the trade-off is conceptualised as a tension between protection of human dignity and the maintenance of deportability as a state interest. The legal lens enables us to see ATR not as humanitarian gestures, but as normative structures that actively shape the rights position of irregularised migrants.

A limitation on the GAPs side is that, within the consortium structure, country-level work packages focus primarily on mapping return legal frameworks and their policy implications, rather than systematically examining alternatives to return as a distinct governance field. This conceptual gap is partly mitigated by our use of the FAiR Project typology, which provides a three-part classification (explicit/semi-explicit/implicit) and offers Greece and Germany as illustrative empirical anchors for these modalities. However, for this concept note, Tukey’s alternatives to return have been analysed directly through its own legal and policy frameworks, rather than taken second-hand. The specific added value of this note is therefore not only that it aligns the three countries with the three ATR modalities, but also that it applies a human-rights trade-off analysis to all three cases in a comparable manner, something neither the GAPs country dossiers nor the FAiR conceptual paper explicitly undertakes.

4. Mapping Existing Alternatives to Return: Selected Country Cases

In contemporary return governance, ATRs are overwhelmingly discussed in relation to irregular migrants, because these are the subjects who are legally removable and thus deportable. This is also why ATR are analytically related to coerced return; coercion is not only physical removal, but also the management of deportability. Therefore, for the country cases, the priority is also given to irregular migration.

Regularisation emerges as the most visible ATR instrument, as it revises the legal status of a deportable person without requiring removal. This is also the most precise point at which ATR can be distinguished from humanitarian protection or resettlement: regularisation converts a deportable into a resident, at least temporarily, thereby suspending the logic of return. By contrast, detention is not an alternative to return, but sits on the coercive side of the same continuum. Yet, detention is an important concept because ATR and detention are embedded in the same institutional repertoire. It is not easy to find a clear, exclusive, and perfect match, because although Greece is a case study in regularisation, it more closely reflects the current situation in Greece today. Between these extremes, states deploy a wide spectrum of graduated coercion techniques, including narrower access to welfare, reporting requirements, work-conditional toleration, and time-bound protections, which, individually, appear ‘administrative’ but, collectively, organise the behaviour of deportable migrants without direct physical force (Eule et al., 2019). In this sense, ATRs are not outside return enforcement but one of its governance modes: they remain embedded in an enforcement architecture that produces irregularity and manages non-removal.

Against this background, we now turn to three contrasting country cases: Greece, Germany, and Turkey, which empirically represent three distinct ATR modalities, as already recognised in the FAiR typology: explicit, semi-explicit and implicit forms (Torres Chedraui et al., 2024), and are analytically relevant for the GAP’s focus on coerced return and the governance of deportable persons. Additionally, the inventory of the FAiR Project (Ince-Beqo, 2024, pp. 39-49, 96-105) benefits the cases of Greece and Germany.

Table 2: Typology of Assisted Temporary Regularisation (ATR) Across Selected Countries

Category	Type of ATR	Country Representative
Explicit	ex-post labour regularisation	Greece
Semi-explicit	codified toleration + conditional conversion	Germany
Implicit/ hybrid	temporal protection etc. + externalised non-return	Turkey

4.1. Greece: Explicit ATR Model

Before starting, our classification of Greece as the paradigmatic example of “explicit ATR” is therefore not intended to suggest that regularisation constitutes the dominant or continuous logic of Greek migration governance over the last three decades. Instead, it reflects the fact that, within the FAiR typology, Greece offers one of the clearest empirical instances of large-scale, employment-linked regularisation being used as a state instrument to manage non-removal, even if this instrument has been mobilised in a highly episodic and conditional manner. As the GAPs Project’s Greek partner rightly emphasises, the massive legalisation campaigns of 1998, 2001 and 2005–06 should be read as three exceptional, time-bound episodes, not as a stable “model” or rule of governance. In between and beyond these moments, irregularisation, detention, spatial containment and informal labour have remained the structural features of the Greek migration regime, with deportability and precarious work operating as the everyday norm rather than as the exception (Hatziprokopiou *et al.*, 2024; Ince-Beqo *et al.*, 2024).

This historical and political context qualifies Greece’s position within the explicit ATR category in at least two ways. First, the regularisation measures themselves were largely reactive, sector-specific and labour-driven, designed to legalise already present retrospectively, already exploited workers, rather than to establish a predictable, rights-based pathway to long-term residence (Kraler, 2019; Ince-Beqo et al., 2024). In this sense, regularisation functioned as a pragmatic tool of labour-market governance and migration control, rather than as a normative

commitment to inclusion. Second, as our Greek colleagues underline, the more recent legal avenues to status based on long-term residence – such as the three-year residence clause adopted to facilitate the regularisation of certain categories of migrants – have already been abolished under the latest legislation, which prioritises return and detention, despite ongoing labour shortages. This legislative reversal confirms that, in today’s Greek context, explicit, large-scale regularisation has become the exception rather than a policy horizon, while asylum procedures and more ad hoc, discretionary statuses constitute the main remaining channels for regularisation.

Methodologically, these reservations do not invalidate the use of Greece as an anchor case for explicit ATR, but they require that our typology be read in ideal-typical rather than descriptive terms. Greece exemplifies how codified, employment-linked regularisation can operate as an explicit alternative to return in specific conjunctures, yet this explicit ATR dimension co-exists with, and is increasingly overshadowed by, a broader regime of irregularisation, detention and deterrence. Situating Greece in the explicit category is, therefore, less a claim about the overall character of Greek migration governance today and more an analytical choice to foreground one historically significant, but temporally and politically limited, modality through which non-removal has been governed. Acknowledging this ambivalence is crucial for our human-rights trade-off analysis: it reminds us that even “explicit” ATR regimes may be deeply restrictive, exceptional, and reversible, and that the protective potential of regularisation must always be evaluated against the broader architecture of coercive return, irregularisation, and informalisation.

In Greece, return governance⁵ is characterised by a long and complex history of formal, informal and irregular removal practices, strongly shaped by national policing logics and EU frameworks. While the Return Directive 2008/115/EC was transposed into Greek law in 2011 (Law 3907/2011), an older administrative expulsion regime under Law 3386/2005 still co-exists, creating legal ambiguity and overlapping competences between different procedures and authorities (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024, pp. 5–6). Multiple institutional actors are involved, including the Ministry of Migration and Asylum, the police, and Frontex. Since 2020, a Directorate of Returns has been established within the Greek Asylum Service; however, police authorities retain decisive operational control, especially regarding detention, return decisions, and removal (Ibid., pp. 19–21). In practice, detention is treated as the rule rather than the exception, including for those with pending protection claims, despite repeated human rights concerns and the ECtHR jurisprudence (Ibid., p. 37). Although Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) programs, delivered by IOM, provide a more humane channel, they remain underfunded relative to forced removals and continue to operate in an environment of coercion (Ibid., p. 6). Return governance in Greece is highly nationality-differentiated: high-recognition nationalities (such as Syrians and Afghans) are positioned differently from those structurally excluded from asylum recognition (including Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Egypt), who are at risk of falling into irregularity (Ince-Beqo et al., 2024, pp. 99, 102). Finally, substantial data inconsistencies and a lack of transparency,

⁵ GAPS Project analysed the return governance of Greece with its legal and policy framework as well as with the return infrastructure. For further information: Hatziprokopiou, P., Kandylis, G., Komita, K., Koutrolikou, P., Papatzani, E., Tramountanis, A. (2024). “Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in Greece. WP2 Country Dossier” in GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10665482; Papatzani, E., Kandylis, G., Hatziprokopiou, P., Koutrolikou, P., Psallidaki, T., Varouxi, Ch., Vezyrgianni, K. (2025) WP3: Return Migration Infrastructures. Country Dossier: Greece. GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working Paper: 2025/17. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15705012. Also, the Comparative Report covers the Greece country case: Gökalp Aras, N. E., Öztürk, N. Ö., Strik, T., Thornburn Stern, R., Trylinska, A., and Yüksel, U. (2024). Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in the EU - Comparative Report, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11222075, <https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/legal-and-policy-infrastructures-of-returns-in-eu-comparative-report-wp2>

combined with allegations of pushbacks and difficulties in distinguishing between “return”, “expulsion”, and “readmission”, are central governance challenges (Ibid., 5–6, 11–13).

In terms of ATR and conceptually, Greece is the most representative case of the explicit ATR model, as regularisation through employment, which is primarily observed in Southern European countries to meet labour-market needs, is evident. The FAiR Projects defines it as “regularisation as “an act of legal integration through which irregular migrants are included in mainstream social and legal structures by means of a legal status” (Kraler 2019, cited in Torres Chedraui et al., 2024, p. 15). Regularisation exists, is widely used on a large scale, and is publicly legislated, but only under conditions linked to labour-market needs.

In the FAiR Inventory Report (Ince-Beqo et al., 2024, pp. 96-105), Greece’s approach to returns is described as historically reactive and labour-driven, in which irregularity is first tolerated in practice and later regularised through large-scale legalisation decrees. The report notes that Greek regularisation has been used as a post hoc mechanism rather than as a rights-based migration model (Ibid., p. 96). Large national regularisation waves, approximately 582,000 persons (1998), 362,000 (2001), and around 200,000 (2005–06) are explicitly listed as core institutional episodes (Ibid., p. 101). These are coded as employment-linked status conversions, since regularisation was conditional on proof of labour insertion. Thus, the main focus of the ATR in Greece is employment-based regularisation to address labour shortages in specific sectors, such as agriculture and construction, and to provide legal pathways to employment for irregular migrants. In this regard, Greece combines both very high irregularity production and periodic large-scale regularisations driven by labour market needs.

Legally and politically, Greece deepened deterrence after 2007, escalating border surveillance and securitisation at the Greek-Turkish land frontier (Evros fence, intensified policing, technological surveillance) (Ibid., pp. 97-98). However, despite this tendency toward enforcement, actual returns remained extremely limited. Only 2,077 people were returned in the post-EU-Turkey Statement period (2016–2023), compared to 39,715 arrivals in 2023 alone (Ibid., p. 99). On the other hand, the February-March 2020 events (known as Pazarkule) at the Turkey-Greece border meant the ‘de facto’ end of the EUTS, and the readmissions were stopped (Gökalp Aras, 2024, p. 15). The last readmission occurred in March 2020, bringing the total to 23 (UNHCR, 2020). According to Turkish official sources, a total of 2,139 returns has been completed under the Statement’s term since March 2016 (PMM, 2021).

Greek migration governance combines strict border militarisation and return rhetoric with employment-linked regularisation programmes (Ince-Beqo, 2024). Parliament reduced the undocumented presence requirement for employment-based regularisation from 7 years to 3 years, unlocking a 3-year residency permit (Ibid., p. 101). However, the new bill on returns and detention (2025) has terminated this possibility. These regularisation programmes of 2023 are not in force. And they probably also functioned more as an exception than as the rule. The report argues that Greece governs deportable irregulars through formal, periodic, labour-linked status conversion, rather than through detention-based compliance or unconditional removal.

Therefore, Greece is classified in the first category as the “explicit” ATR type, where regularisation is openly legislated and legal, but it is conditional, intermittent, and instrumental (Ibid., pp. 96–101). Return is officially affirmed in political discourse, but employment-based regularisation is the operative instrument through which the Greek state governs non-removal. This makes Greece neither a humanitarian “regularisation state” nor an implicitly tolerant one; instead, it is a model in which the state maintains a strict return/deterrence narrative while simultaneously designing structured legal pathways only for irregular migrants who can demonstrate continued labour utility (agriculture, construction).

4.2. Germany: Semi-Explicit ATR Model

Germany's return governance⁶ is framed by a constant political push to increase the return rate expressed through more than 35 amendments to asylum and residence law, and accompanied by increasingly restrictive rhetoric that connects deportability to domestic security concerns (Mielke et al., 2024, p. 9). This focus is primarily on rejected asylum seekers and deportable subjects to demonstrate the state's steering capacity (Ibid.). There is significant discursive and policy continuity across governments, with the current coalition (CDU, CSU and SPD.) retaining a strong emphasis on 'effective returns' despite signalling a new paradigm (Ibid.). At the level of legal infrastructure, Germany has transposed the EU Return Directive since 2008; however, its implementation remains ambivalent according to the GAPs Project analysis. For example, operationally, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) case law is often more protective and influential than domestic statutory law (Ibid., p. 3). Multi-level governance makes return enforcement highly complex, as 16 federal states and their local administrative bodies carry enforcement responsibility, including detention, while federal ministries negotiate migration agreements, set legal frameworks, and fund assistance programmes (Ibid., p. 13). Structural problems span legislation, institutions, operational practices, data sharing, implementation and political communication (Ibid., p. 3). Forced return is operationalised via expulsion (Sec. 53 AufenthG) and deportation orders (Sec. 58a AufenthG; Sec. 34a AsylG), with the Federal Police executing removals, including to safe third countries (Dublin) (Ibid., pp. 28–29). Detention remains a central enforcement tool, despite evidence of its unlawful use and despite the principle that detention should be a last resort (Ibid., p. 3, 12, 35). At the same time, regularisation is possible when deportation is not enforceable, via temporary suspension of deportation (Duldung) (Sec. 60a-d AufenthG) and later residence permits in specific cases (Sec. 25.3, Sec. 25a–b AufenthG) (Ibid., p. 35). Overall, Germany has a system in which return governance is highly legalised and bureaucratised, yet internally contradictory, uneven across states, and riddled with operational gaps. It is a system in which deportability is legally sustained, yet complete removal is often not possible, thus producing Germany's central ATR space: formalised toleration (Duldung) as the semi-explicit tool for governing non-removal.

In the adopted tripartite ATR classification, Germany best fits the second type because its primary alternative to return is not an explicit rights-based regularisation (as in labour amnesties), nor an informal practice. Instead, Germany's hallmark is a codified, rule-bound, and conditional toleration regime (Duldung) that acknowledges non-removal while withholding full membership; it then channels selected deportable persons toward tightly specified transition tracks, such as training, steady employment, and integration performance, which may culminate in time-limited or longer-term residence (Mielke et al., 2024). The administrative nature, conditionality, and preservation of deportability are precisely what fit the semi-explicit model. It is semi-explicit, because Germany operationalises structured non-removal through administrative toleration and graduated legalisation, rather than through either blanket regularisations or implicit tolerance (Ince-Beqo et al., 2024).

In Germany, Duldung is the formal instrument that temporarily suspends deportation without granting a residence title. Legally, it is grounded in Sec. 60a AufenthG and may be issued on

⁶ GAPS Project analysed the return governance of Germany with its legal and policy framework as well as with the return infrastructure. For further information: Mielke K., Mencütek, Z.S., & Wolf, D. (2024) "Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in Germany. WP2 Country Dossier" in GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10671530; Mielke, K., Vollmer, R., Wolf, D., & Mencütek, Z. S. (2025) "Return Migration Infrastructures I Germany – The case of the federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia. WP3 Country Dossier" GAPs: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working paper 2025/12. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15193348. Also, the Comparative Report covers the Greece country case: Gökalp Aras, N. E., Öztürk, N. Ö., Strik, T., Thornburn Stern, R., Trylinska, A., and Yüksel, U. (2024). Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in the EU - Comparative Report, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11222075.

grounds of international law, for humanitarian reasons, or to safeguard political interests (Mielke et al., 2024, p. 28). Also regulated in Sec. 60a of the Residence Act is the *Duldung*, which is granted when deportation is impossible for legal or factual reasons (e.g., lack of travel documents). This is the most common form of *Duldung*. While the obligation to leave remains in force, deportation cannot be carried out as long as the obstacle persists, and the suspension can be revoked at any time by the competent authority (Ibid., pp. 28–29). In practice, this produces a long-term series of renewals, the so-called *Kettenduldung* (lit: chain toleration; *ibid.*, p. 29). One unique legal innovation that Germany established in 2022 as a pathway out of chain toleration is the Opportunity Residence Right (Sec. 104c AufenthaltG). As of May 2025, 84,206 persons had been granted the opportunity to reside; of these, 16,646 received a succeeding residence permit (according to Sec. 25a/b Residence Act), while 31,372 grantees were still in the 18-month grant period (Mediendienst Integration, 2025). At the start of the programme, 137,000 tolerated migrants in Germany had resided for more than five years in the country and were thus considered qualified to apply for opportunity residence grants (Peitz and Carwehl, 2025, p. 2) – out of a total of 248,000 tolerated migrants residing in Germany at the end of 2022 (Ibid.). The Government of Germany estimated in 2022 (and legitimised the Opportunity Residence Right’s legal initiative with it) that 98,000 out of the theoretically eligible 137,000 migrants would apply for this particular regularisation measure (Mediendienst Integration, 2025).

The FAiR Inventory (Ince-Beqo et al., 2024, p. 43) conceptualises *Duldung* as a “limbo status” that addresses non-deportability without legalising the category, but de facto recognises presence. Public authorities themselves sometimes classify *Duldung* holders as irregular, and the stock of persons under *Duldung* was approximately 248,000 at the end of 2022 (Ibid.). The inventory also highlights how *Duldung* creates a liminal status that can persist for years, with progression out of toleration being conditioned by integration and labour-market performance rather than by a rights-based regularisation logic (Ibid.). Notably, the GAPs report confirms that about four out of five persons ordered to leave ultimately end up with *Duldung* status rather than being removed (Mielke et al., 2024, p. 28). This shows that *Duldung* is not marginal; it is structurally central to German return governance.

Duldung also contains variant forms with explicit policy functions. Besides the *Chancenaufenthaltsrecht* (Opportunity Residence Right), which, since 2022, provided a stay perspective beyond *Duldung* but ends in its current form on 1 January 2026, Germany’s ATR repertoire formalises graduated inclusion through two prominent bridges:

1. **Ausbildungsduldung** (training-linked toleration): suspends deportation for the duration of a recognised vocational training programme (typically 3 years) and may be followed by a two-year residence permit when the graduate secures employment in the trained occupation. *Ausbildungsduldung* (Sec. 60c AufenthaltG) suspends deportation during a three-year vocational training period and may lead to a two-year residence permit if employment is subsequently secured (Ince-Beqo et al., 2024, pp. 44-45).
2. **Beschäftigungsduldung** (employment-linked toleration): targets individuals with at least 12 months of suspension and at least 18 months of lawful employment; it can be extended up to 30 months, with potential further extension if strict conditions continue to be met (stable employment, integration, and no serious offences). It was introduced in 2020 (Sec. 60d AufenthaltG); unlike normal *Duldung*, persons under this scheme cannot be deported during its validity (Ibid., p. 45). A further variant, “*Duldung-light*” (Sec. 60b AufenthaltG), applies to persons whose identity cannot be verified (Mielke et al., 2024, p. 29).

In the FAiR inventory (Ince-Beqo et al., 2024), Germany is portrayed as a high-capacity enforcement state that nonetheless governs large numbers of deportable persons through structured non-removal, rather than continuous physical removal. This governance is centred on toleration and a set of codified bridges from toleration to time-limited residence,

complemented by Assisted Voluntary Return/Reintegration (AVR) and Temporary Protection (TP) for specific groups. Moreover, given that the new government coalition of CDU-CSU and SPD is determined to replace the *Chancenaufenthaltsrecht* with a legal provision (KOAV, 2025) that focuses exclusively on highly integrated and self-sustaining foreigners who immigrated as of 31 December 2024, the majority of foreigners will be subject to deportability in the future. Therefore, this country case refers to a semi-explicit model, in which removal remains the formal endpoint, but day-to-day administration proceeds through conditional, revocable inclusion that preserves deportability.

4.3. Turkey: Implicit/ Hybrid ATR Model

Turkey represents a distinct and analytically separate type of alternative to return, not because it employs temporary protection as such, but because of how non-removal is structured, governed, and sustained over time. Unlike EU-based protection regimes, which explicitly suspend deportability within a rights-based legal framework, Turkey's non-removal regime operates through prolonged temporality, extensive administrative discretion, and the systematic preservation of deportability as a governing principle. Temporary protection, humanitarian residence permits, and international protection procedures in Turkey do not function as pathways toward secure legal inclusion, but rather as instruments of managed non-return that maintain legal uncertainty and revocability. What defines the Turkish case, therefore, is not the existence of protection statuses, but the way temporariness itself is institutionalised as a mode of governance. This produces a hybrid ATR model in which non-removal is achieved without extinguishing deportability, and where protection operates within a broader architecture of conditionality, discretion, and fragmented rights.

This governance logic is further reinforced by the externalisation of EU return policies, most notably through the EU–Turkey Statement. However, externalisation should be understood here as a driver and amplifier of Turkey's implicit ATR regime rather than as its defining typological feature. The distinctiveness of the Turkish model lies in how temporality and discretion structure everyday non-removal, while EU conditionality shapes the institutional environment within which this model operates.

Turkey's return governance⁷ has developed into a dense, multi-layered system that sits at the intersection of domestic migration law (especially the 2013 Law on Foreigners and International Protection, LFIP), mass-protection practices for Syrians, and the EU–Turkey Statement of 2016. What makes Turkey distinctive in this context is that it is at once a country of origin (for some groups), a transit point (İçduygu and Aksel, 2015), and increasingly a long-term host (Kaya, 2023). Thus, return is not merely a technical “send people back” question; it is a tool inside a broader management regime for very large and diverse populations (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025a).

The Law on Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP) (Law No. 6458) remains the legal backbone of the system, as it established the civilian migration authority (originally the DGMM, now the Presidency of Migration Management - PMM) and unified the procedures for entry, stay, removal, and international protection in a single statutory framework. In addition, another important aspect regarding Turkey's migration management and,

⁷ GAPS Project analysed the return governance of Turkey with its legal and policy framework as well as with the return infrastructure. For further information: Gökalp Aras, N. E., Yüksel, U. Ünay, H. And Öztürk, N. Ö. (2025a). “Return Migration from Turkey to Syria and Afghanistan”. WP4 Country Report in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15053867; Gökalp Aras, N. E., Yüksel, U. and Ünay, H. (2025b). “Return Migration Infrastructure Turkey: Europe to Europe”. WP3 Country Report in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working paper 2025/20. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15850973.

consequently, return practices is temporary protection. Although temporary protection derives its source from the LFIP (Article 91), it is regulated by a separate regulation, the Temporary Protection Regulation (TPR). The TPR establishes a specific protection framework, currently effective for Syrians, which, by definition, is provisional and revocable, thereby ensuring that return, particularly in organised or “voluntary” forms, remains a viable policy option for the authorities (Mencütek, 2022).

Turkey’s return governance represents the third modality of ATR identified in this framework: implicit or hybrid non-removal. Unlike Greece, where periodic regularisation reflects an explicit and rights-based form of inclusion, or Germany, where Duldung institutionalises semi-explicit administrative toleration, Turkey’s model is structured around temporary, discretionary, and politically contingent non-removal. Deportability is not eliminated but managed through temporality, and protection mechanisms operate within a framework of graduated coercion rather than legal permanence (Mencütek, 2022; Gökalp Aras et al., 2025b).

Additionally, Turkey’s non-removal architecture is shaped by EU externalisation logics, most notably the EU–Turkey Statement (EUTRS, 2016), which situates non-return within a broader externalised return conditionality rather than within domestic regularisation instruments. Turkey can be situated in the implicit category of ATR because return-related practices function not primarily through formalised, legally codified alternatives, but rather through structural irregularization, externalised pressures, and indirect coercion, which together create de facto spaces in which return is governed without being explicitly framed as offering alternatives.

This logic is reinforced in the GAPs WP4 Country Dossier on Turkey, the report highlights that return governance in Turkey generates differentiated irregularity, particularly for Afghans, via pushbacks, accelerated removals, non-arrival policies, and coercive “voluntariness”, all underpinned by legal precarity rather than legalised alternatives (Gökalp Aras et al. 2025: 30–32, 44–50, 60–61). The dossier explicitly notes that Turkey’s return infrastructure is largely shaped by the EU externalisation instruments, especially the EUTRS and the EU Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT), which have funded and operationalised a national return mechanism while sidestepping explicit regularisation as a core tool (Gökalp Aras et al., 2025: pp. 60–61). This means that what functions in practice as ATR in Turkey is not a deliberate legal pathway away from deportation, but a form of calculated toleration under coercive externalised pressure, which is exactly the type of “implicit” mode that FAIR identifies.

Turkey is neither an explicit ATR jurisdiction (where regularisation schemes are formalised, as in Greece) nor a semi-explicit enforcement regime (as in Germany’s Duldung), but rather a case in which ATR emerges indirectly from structural irregularisation and externalised EU return governance. This combination (EU conditionality, return infrastructure financed by FRIT, and the blurring between “voluntary” and coerced return) is the principal reason Turkey logically falls into the implicit ATR category. In short, Turkey fits the FAiR implicit modality because deportability is symbolically affirmed but practically deferred (Ince-Beqo et al., 2024, pp. 16–17), and non-removal is governed through temporality, fragmentation, and externalisation rather than through “regularisation as legal integration.”

4.3.1 Return and Deportation under the LFIP

Under Turkish law, removal from the territory occurs through two principal mechanisms: (i) refusal of entry and return at the border for those who have not legally entered the country, and (ii) deportation following a formal deportation decision (sınır dışı etme kararı). Once a deportation decision becomes final, either upon expiry of the seven-day judicial-appeal period or after the administrative court has ruled, the decision is enforceable without any further administrative act (LFIP Art. 53). Judicial review is carried out by administrative courts,

whose rulings are final and non-appealable, and enforcement is suspended until finalisation (LFIP Art. 53).

The legal grounds for deportation are explicitly enumerated in the Turkish law (Article 54 LFIP) yet even when these conditions are met, removal cannot be ordered if the individual falls under the non-removability clauses of Article 55 of the LFIP; including, *inter alia*, those facing risk of torture or inhuman treatment, individuals whose health, age, or pregnancy makes travel impossible, or victims of trafficking and violence. These exceptions reflect the principle of proportionality under Article 13 of the Turkish Constitution and the non-refoulement principle under Turkey's international human rights obligations.

4.3.2. Legally Non-Removable Persons

From a legal perspective, individuals who cannot be removed from Turkey fall broadly into five categories:

1. Those explicitly protected under LFIP Art. 55;
2. Those whose removal would breach the 'balancing requirement' between public interest and fundamental rights sought the necessity and proportionality criteria applicable to the restriction of the fundamental rights (Constitution Art. 13);
3. Those against whom a deportation decision has been issued but later found incompatible with Article. 55 (LFIP Implementing Regulation, Art. 57);
4. Those who have applied for international protection while in an irregular situation (LFIP; Arts 8 and 65), and
5. Those who have applied for temporary protection while in an irregular situation (LFIP, Art. 91).

Although Turkish legislation does not create a separate category of non-removables, these individuals are governed through a patchwork of formal and informal instruments, many of which operate within wide administrative discretion (Doğar, 2017).

4.3.3. Humanitarian Residence Permit as a Legal Tool of Non-Removal

The primary statutory mechanism for regularising the stay of non-removable persons is the humanitarian residence permit (LFIP, Article 46) (Aydoğan Elçin and Erşanlı, 2021). This permit may be granted when deportation is not possible or reasonable, when judicial review is pending, or when it is in the child's best interest. It thus serves a dual function: (i) to regularise the presence of those whom Turkey must allow to remain, and (ii) to provide a temporary, revocable status for persons who cannot currently be deported.

However, the humanitarian residence permit does not confer a protection status in the conventional sense; it merely regularises residence without guaranteeing long-term stability (Öztürk and Ovacık, 2024, p. 154). Its issuance depends heavily on administrative discretion and therefore provides limited legal predictability. The permit is valid only until the removal obstacle ceases or a "safe country" for deportation is identified (LFIP Implementing Reg. Art. 57). Even then, the underlying deportation decision remains in force, meaning deportability persists in law.

This reflects the broader logic of temporariness in Turkish return governance: the humanitarian permit embodies the non-refoulement obligation in practice, but it is not institutionalised as a rights-based alternative to return.

4.3.4. International and Temporary Protection as De Facto ATR Mechanisms

Persons who apply for international protection or temporary protection are also shielded from removal while their applications are pending. In principle, these mechanisms suspend deportability rather than permanently extinguish it. Yet, in practice, they function as implicit ATR instruments, particularly for groups such as Afghans, who are formally removable but cannot be returned due to political or practical barriers (Gökalp Aras et al., 2025b).

For Afghan asylum-seekers, recognition rates remain low, and applications often merely postpone removal rather than result in durable status (Gökalp Aras et al., 2025b). Such individuals exemplify politically deportable but temporarily non-removable persons. Their continued presence is tolerated through administrative liminality rather than legal certainty (Mencütek, 2022).

Similarly, the temporary protection regime for Syrians, while derived from LFIP Art. 91 and regulated by the Temporary Protection Regulation (TPR), institutionalises a politically conditional non-removal. The TPR lacks a specific guarantee against expulsion comparable to that provided to international protection applicants under Article 32 of the 1951 Convention and similarly under Article. 54(2) of the LFIP. Its continuation or termination depends on executive discretion, particularly the President’s authority to end the regime (TPR Art. 11/2). Thus, protection is maintained not as a right but as a revocable administrative measure, and the possibility of “voluntary” or organised return remains structurally embedded.

4.3.5. Additional Legal Tools

Other limited forms of regularisation include the residence permit for victims of human trafficking (LFIP Arts. 48–49), issued irrespective of immigration status and renewable for up to three years. Between 2019 and 2023, 1,469 individuals were identified as victims of human trafficking, and 973 of these individuals benefited from victim support services (PMM 2024: 67). While this serves as a humane alternative to removal, its short duration and dependency on identification processes constrain its protective function.

4.3.6. Informal and De Facto Practices

Beyond the law, Turkey’s migration governance is characterised by administrative flexibility and informal tolerance. Two prominent practices stand out:

1. Tolerated presence without status: many non-removable persons, particularly rejected Afghan applicants, remain in Turkey without formal status or a residence permit, relying on de facto tolerance (Gökalp Aras et al., 2025a). Studies show that Afghan mobility is managed not through formal removal, but through a combination of structural irregularization, police surveillance, and geographically constrained permissiveness (Karadağ and Sert, 2023). Karadağ and Sert’s (2023) research documents how Afghans navigate a landscape of fragmented enforcement, police checkpoints, and periodic crackdowns, which leave them legally deportable but practically immobile. This tolerated irregularity constitutes a feature of Turkey’s hybrid non-removal model.
2. Administrative supervision without legal basis: for persons whose temporary protection has been revoked (TPR Art. 8), authorities often confine them to accommodation centres without a formal removal or detention order, amounting to de facto administrative control without legal underpinning (Gökalp Aras et al., 2025a; Öztürk and Öztürk, 2023; GAPs-SEP, 2024).

4.3.7. Turkey as a Hybrid Non-Removal Regime

Taken together, these features position Turkey as an implicit or hybrid ATR system, in which deportability is suspended but structurally preserved. Non-removal is achieved through temporary, discretionary, and externally influenced mechanisms rather than through rights-based inclusion. The state governs mobility through a temporal containment of returnability, a hallmark of the “third ATR modality” identified in this study.

Thus, Turkey’s migration governance embodies graduated coercion: individuals are not forcibly expelled but remain within an architecture that conditions legality on compliance and preserves the latent threat of removal. This governance form aligns with the GAPs framework of *managed non-return* and illustrates how ATR can become instruments of control rather than of durable protection (Eule et al., 2019).

5. Human Rights Trade-Off Analysis

The comparative reading of Greece, Germany, and Turkey demonstrates that ATR (though often presented as humane or pragmatic substitutes for deportation) constitute complex governance instruments through which states balance the protection of individual rights against the maintenance of deportability as a sovereign prerogative. In practice, these policies reveal deep trade-offs between control and care, legality and liminality, protection and conditionality (Şahin Mencütek and Triandafyllidou, 2024; Carrera and Cortinovis, 2019; Gökalp Aras et al., 2025a, 2025b).

Across all three cases, the human-rights dimension of ATR manifests in three interlocking tensions: the tension between legal inclusion and political temporariness; between procedural safeguards and administrative discretion; and between equality and selective conditionality. The human-rights trade-off analysis proposed here assesses these tensions across five dimensions: intentionality, transparency, rights breadth, temporal proportionality, and equality/non-discrimination, and shows how each national regime reconfigures the boundaries of lawful presence without fully severing the coercive logic of return.

5.1 Intentionality of Non-Removal

In all three regimes, non-removal is not primarily designed as a rights-protective measure but as a state strategy of deferred enforcement.

- In Greece, employment-based regularisation operates *post factum*, rewarding economic contribution rather than recognising entitlement to stay, transforming protection into an instrument of labour governance (Ince-Beqo et al., 2024).
- In Germany, *Duldung* formalises toleration while maintaining the legal obligation to leave, thus institutionalising a codified limbo in which legality is suspended but never fully granted (Mielke et al., 2024).
- In Turkey, international protection, temporary protection, and humanitarian residence permit suspend deportability but maintain the legal and political viability of return, especially under the EU–Turkey Statement, where non-removal is embedded within externalised return conditionality (Mencütek, 2022).

This reveals that ATR mechanisms are rarely constructed as ends in themselves; instead, they mediate deportability through time-bound or conditional inclusion.

5.2 Transparency and Legal Certainty

From a human-rights standpoint, legal predictability and transparency are prerequisites for protecting dignity and due process.

- Greece’s codified but episodic regularisation waves provide visibility without continuity, creating dependence on shifting political and economic cycles.
- Germany’s multi-tiered toleration regime is transparent in law but opaque in practice, as pathways from *Duldung* to residence are complex, conditional, and unevenly applied across Länder.
- Turkey’s hybrid system epitomises opacity: the Temporary Protection Regulation and the grant of humanitarian residence permits offer administrative flexibility, but little foreseeability for migrants, whose legal status depends on executive discretion.

The result is a pervasive sense of legal insecurity that conflicts with the principle of legal certainty under international human-rights law.

5.3 Breadth and Quality of Rights

The tension between the state's need for flexibility and the individual's entitlement to substantive rights becomes most visible in the limited and conditional rights attached to ATR statuses.

- In Greece, regularisation offers access to employment and social benefits but remains instrumentally linked to labour utility, excluding those unable to demonstrate economic contribution.
- In Germany, *Duldung* holders face restricted welfare access, mobility limits, and continuous reporting obligations, reflecting a calibrated balance between tolerance and control (Eule et al., 2019).
- In Turkey, temporary protection provides access to basic services (education, health, and limited work permits) but excludes pathways to secure residence or participate in politics, thereby reinforcing stratified membership (Bjorklund Belliveau and Ferguson, 2023; Ihlamur-Öner, 2022; Öztürk, 2017).

In all three, rights are conditional, reversible, and partial, contravening the non-discrimination principles in ICCPR Art. 2(2) and ECHR Art. 14.

5.4 Temporal Proportionality

International human-rights standards require that any restriction on liberty or residence be proportionate and temporally limited. Yet, ATR regimes often convert temporary measures into enduring ones.

- Greece's recurrent amnesties institutionalise a cycle of irregularity and periodic legalisation.
- Germany's *Kettenduldung* (repeated extensions of toleration) creates permanent temporariness, eroding the predictability that human-rights law demands (Mielke et al., 2024).
- Turkey's "temporary" protection, now in its second decade, has become a structural condition of containment, where temporariness is prolonged by political discretion rather than objective necessity (Öztürk, 2020; Ulusoy et al., 2025).

Such chronically suspended legality and prolonged liminality undermine migrants' access to the rights to private and family life, education, and social security, violating the principle of proportionality embedded in ECHR jurisprudence.

5.5 Equality and Non-Discrimination

The stratification of rights across nationality, gender, and status is a defining human rights trade-off in ATR regimes.

- Greece prioritises economically active irregular migrants; Germany differentiates inclusion based on "integration performance"; Turkey differentiates by nationality and political utility, particularly favouring Syrians over Afghans (Almasri, 2023; ProAsyl, 2021).
- These distinctions perpetuate a hierarchy of "deservingness," contrary to the universalist premises of human rights protection (Welfens, 2023).

5.6 Normative Synthesis

Taken together, these findings reveal that alternatives to return mitigate the immediate harm of forced removal but simultaneously entrench new layers of precariousness. By translating human-rights commitments into instruments of conditional governance, states convert protection into compliance. The equilibrium between enforcement and dignity, the normative axis of ATR, leans heavily toward the former.

A cross-cutting human-rights concern that emerges from all three ATR regimes is the risk that prolonged liminality itself becomes a coercive force. When migrants are kept in legally uncertain or indefinitely renewable temporary statuses, the cumulative effects of restricted mobility, limited rights, and the absence of pathways to long-term residence may generate structural pressure toward “choosing” return. This dynamic is observable across all three national contexts, though it manifests with different intensities.

In Turkey, empirical research shows that non-removable groups living in precarious legality (as in the case of Afghans) or in prolonged temporariness (as in the case of Syrians) face conditions under which “voluntariness” collapses into structural coercion. Prolonged irregularity, the lack of legal certainty to obtain gradual access to more secure statuses, and the withdrawal of basic services pose the risk of leading many to sign voluntary return forms despite fearing return (Mencütek, 2022; Karadağ and Sert, 2023; Alpes et al., 2017). In such circumstances, liminality operates not as a benign administrative condition but as a mechanism that transforms non-removal into *constructive refoulement* (Mathew, 2019; Negishi, 2021; Rodenhäuseri, 2023).

In Germany, rights protections and procedural safeguards are comparatively stronger, yet long-term *Duldung* produces a form of “regulated precarity” in which migrants experience sustained pressure to either comply with integration-performance conditions or to consider return when the likelihood of secure residence remains remote. In Greece, recurrent cycles of irregularisation between episodic regularisations similarly create periods in which limited access to services and labour-market vulnerabilities may indirectly encourage acceptance of return programmes.

Thus, although the modalities differ, the comparative pattern is clear: ATR-generated liminality can accumulate coercive effects, blurring the line between voluntary and compelled return. From a human rights perspective, this structural risk must be taken into account in any proportionality assessment of ATR regimes, particularly in relation to the prohibition on refoulement. Disproportionate or cumulatively restrictive conditions that induce return, whether through material deprivation, withdrawal of legal status, or chronic uncertainty, risk invalidating voluntariness and thereby engaging states’ non-refoulement obligations. When rights restrictions become excessive or cumulative, they exert coercive pressure that invalidates voluntariness, thereby transforming an ostensibly voluntary return into constructive refoulement⁸.

From a rights-based perspective, a legitimate alternative to return should satisfy five minimum conditions:

1. Predictability of status through clear procedural safeguards
2. Access to substantive rights without behavioural conditionality
3. Predictability to access gradually secure statuses
4. Strengthening effective rights-based return governance by prioritising voluntariness of the return through effective procedural safeguards and robust monitoring
5. Reversibility of state discretion subject to judicial oversight.

Measured against these standards, the three national models reveal a persistent deficit of legal certainty and equality. While ATR policies reduce overt coercion, they often extend enforcement through temporality, producing governance forms that are humanitarian in appearance but disciplinary in function (Andersson, 2014; Tazzioli, 2020b; Eule et al., 2019). The human-rights trade-off perspective exposes ATR as a double-edged architecture: it lessens direct violations of non-refoulement but expands the state’s capacity to govern through

⁸ *M.S. v. Belgium*, App. No. 50012/08, 31.01.2012, para. 124; *N.A. v. Finland*, App. No. 25244/18, 14.02.2020, para.60 (This judgment was revised in accordance with Rule 80 of the Rules of Court in a judgment of 13 July 2021).

uncertainty. The core normative dilemma is whether ATR regimes can fulfil their protective promise without normalising permanent liminality. A rights-consistent approach would require embedding proportionality tests, procedural transparency, and equality guarantees into all non-removal instruments. Only then can ATR transform from mechanisms of graduated coercion into genuine pathways of dignified non-return.

6. Discussions and Conclusion

This concept note has shown that ATR are not marginal exceptions but a structurally embedded dimension of European return governance. Both the empirical data from the GAPs Project for the Turkey case and the FAiR Project's cross-country evidence confirm that only around 23% of return orders are enforced, meaning that non-return is the norm, not the residual anomaly, and that European states govern large populations of deportable non-removed persons every year (FAiR, 2025). In this context, ATR should not be conceptualised as humanitarian "alternatives" in a normative sense, but rather as differentiated modes of governing deportability when removal cannot be achieved in practice.

By mapping three analytically distinct models: Greece's explicit labour-linked regularisation, Germany's semi-explicit administrative toleration, and Turkey's implicit/hybrid temporality-based non-removal, it is evident that ATR are diverse techniques of structured non-removal. They differ in terms of visibility, legal codification, eligibility, and the degree to which they mitigate or reinforce coercive pressures. ATR can produce social stability, reduce exploitation, and support economic participation; yet, they can also perpetuate insecurity when pathways remain discretionary, temporary, or narrowly defined (Ibid.). Thus, it can be said that ATR operates on a double frontier, functioning both as rights-expanding and rights-containing instruments.

This is why a human-rights trade-off analysis is indispensable. Whether ATR expands substantive rights or produces "graduated coercion" (Eule et al., 2019) cannot be assumed; it must be measured. The question is not whether non-return exists; non-return is already a structural fact. However, the question remains whether the mechanisms managing it increase certainty, equality, and access to rights, or instead reproduce liminality, fear, and conditionality.

In this regard, there is a need to explicitly recognise non-return as a governance reality rather than a political failure. Additionally, the eligibility criteria for ATR should be simplified, broadened, and linked to stable residence outcomes to prevent cyclical irregularization. Thus, ATR reforms should move beyond ad hoc discretion towards predictable, transparent, durable status outcomes.

Finally, the concept note highlights significant gaps in future research. Academic and policy literature has remarkably limited comparative knowledge on (1) the actual rights impacts of different ATR modalities, (2) the role of externalisation in producing hybrid ATR (as in Turkey), and (3) the political economies of non-removal, especially labour-market driven toleration. These gaps mean that future research should move from merely describing legal categories to empirically assessing how different ATR modalities actually transform (or fail to transform) lived rights conditions on the ground.

In this sense, this concept note serves only as an analytical foundation. The next step, applying a systematic human-rights trade-off analysis to three distinct ATR models, is not only a scientific task but also a necessary policy intervention for a European return field that is still largely governed by the denial of non-return, rather than by evidence-based regulation.

7. References

- Almasri, S. (2023). "Why is Syria a War but Not Afghanistan? Nationality-based Aid and Protection in Turkey's Syria Refugee Response." *Refugee Survey Quarterly*, 42(1), 29-54.
- Alpes, M. J., Tunaboylu, S., Ulusoy, O., and Hassan, S. (2017). Post-deportation risks under the EU-Turkey statement: What happens after readmission to Turkey?, <https://cadmus.eui.eu/server/api/core/bitstreams/39505537-5746-5e89-892f-3c232b7420a7/content>
- Andersson, R. (2014). "Time and the migrant other: European border controls and the temporal economics of illegality." *American Anthropologist*, 116(4), 795-809.
- Aydoğan Elçin D., and Erşanlı O. (2021). Yabancıların İnsan Haklarının İhlalinde Bir Koruma Mekanizması Olarak İnsani İkamet İzni, Ankara Barosu Hukuk Kurultayı, pp.809-834.
- BAMF (2023). Migration Report 2023. Federal Office for Migration and Refugees. <https://www.bamf.de/SharedDocs/Anlagen/EN/Forschung/Migrationsberichte/migrationsbericht-2023.html?nn=447198>
- Biorklund Belliveau L., and Ferguson R. (2023). "Normalising the Exceptional: The Use of Temporary Protection in Transit Countries to Externalise Borders and Responsibilities." *Geopolitics* 28(1): 333-363.
- Carrera, S., Stefan, M., Cortinovis, R., & Luk, N. C. (2019). When mobility is not a choice: Problematising asylum seekers' secondary movements and their criminalisation in the EU, <https://repository.ua.ac/entities/publication/a1b581aa-0d71-4391-9578-e958f3f98072>
- Carrera, S. and Geddes, A. (eds.) (2021). *The EU Pact on Migration and Asylum in light of the United Nations*, <https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/EU-pact-migration-asylum-global-compact-refugees.pdf>
- Doğar, D. (2017). "Against all odds: Turkey's response to 'undesirable but unreturnable' asylum-seekers." *Refugee Survey Quarterly*, 36(1), 107-125.
- Eule, T. G., Borrelli, L. M., Lindberg, A., and Wyss, A. (2019). *Migrants Before the Law*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- EUAA. (2024). Guidelines on Alternatives to Detention, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, https://euaa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publications/2025-01/2024_Guidelines_on_Alternatives_to_Detention_EN.pdf
- Eurostat. (2025). "Returns to third countries up by 13% in Q2 2025". <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/w/ddn-20250930-3>
- FaiR. (2025). Work Package 6: Alternatives to return- Key Findings, <https://fair-return.org/findings-reccomendations/>
- Flynn, M. (2019). The Debate over Alternatives to Immigration Detention of Children, Global Detention Project Publication, <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Flynn-Debate-over-alternatives-UNIGE-2017.pdf>
- FRA. (2015). Alternatives to detention for asylum seekers and people in return procedures, https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2015-alternatives-to-detention-compilation-key-materials-2_en.pdf

GAPs Project Stakeholder Expert Meeting (SEP), 19 January 2024.

GDP. (2025). 2204 Annual Report, <https://www.globaldetentionproject.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/GDP-ANNUAL-REPORT-2024-Web-1.pdf>

Gökalp Aras, N. E. (2024). “Readmission Agreements and the Evolving Landscape of the Externalised EU Return Policies: The Case of Turkey” in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13134114, https://zenodo.org/records/13134114/files/D2.2_GAPs_WP2_%20Externalisation%20Working%20Paper_TR.pdf?download=1

Gökalp Aras, N. E., Öztürk, N. Ö., Strik, T., Thornburn Stern, R., Trylinska, A., and Yüksel, U. (2024). Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in the EU - Comparative Report, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11222075, <https://www.returnmigration.eu/wp-series/legal-and-policy-infrastructures-of-returns-in-eu-comparative-report-wp2>

Gökalp Aras, N. E., Yüksel, U., Ünay, H. And Öztürk, N. Ö. (2025a). “Return Migration from Turkey to Syria and Afghanistan”. WP4 Country Report in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15053867, https://zenodo.org/records/15053930/files/D4.1_GAPs%20WP4_Turkey%20Country%20Dossier.pdf?download=1

Gökalp Aras, N. E., Yüksel, U. and Ünay, H. (2025b). “Return Migration Infrastructure Turkey: Europe to Europe”. WP3 Country Report in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working paper 2025/20. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15850973, https://zenodo.org/records/15850973/files/D3.1_WP3_Turkey_Country_Dossier.pdf?download=1

Guild, E., Costello, C., Garlick, M., and Moreno-Lax, V. (2017). The 2015 Refugee Crisis in the European Union. CEPS Paperback Series. Centre for European Policy Studies, https://cdn.ceps.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/CEPS%20PB332%20Refugee%20Crisis%20in%20EU_o.pdf

Hatziprokopiou, P., Kandyli, G., Komita, K., Koutrolidou, P., Papatzani, E., and Tramountanis, A. (2024). “Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in Greece. WP2 Country Dossier” in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10665482

İçduygu, A. (2015). Turkey’s Evolving Migration Policies: A Mediterranean Transit Stop at the

Karadağ, S., and Sert, D. Ş. (2023). “(Non-) deport to discipline: The daily life of Afghans in Turkey.” *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 36(3), 449-466.

Kaya, A. (2023). The world’s leading refugee host, Turkey, has a complex migration history. Migration Policy Institute, 1.

KOAV. (2025). Koalitionsvertrag zwischen CDU, CSU und SPD: Verantwortung für Deutschland. 21. Legislaturperiode. Berlin. https://www.koalitionsvertrag2025.de/sites/www.koalitionsvertrag2025.de/files/koav_2025.pdf

Ihlamur-Öner, S.G. (2022). "The Global Politics of Refugee Protection and Return: The Case of the Syrian Refugees," In *The Informalisation of the EU's External Action in the Field of Migration and Asylum*, E. Kasotti and N. Idriz (eds), pp. 287-315. The Hague: Asser Press.

Ince-Beqo, G., Ambrosini, M., Torres, A. M., Conte, C., and McLean, A. (2025). WP6 Contribution to D9.5 and D9.4: Inventory of Existing Alternatives to Returns Policies D. 6.1, https://fair-return.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/D6.1_M15_Working-Paper_UMIL.pdf

Kraler, A. (2019). "Regularisation: A Misguided Approach or Part and Parcel of a Comprehensive Migration Policy?" *International Migration*, 57(4), 217–233, <https://www.icmpd.org/file/download/48250/file/Regularisation>

Lindberg, A. (2022). *Deportation limbo: State violence and contestations in the Nordics*, Manchester University Press, Oxford.

Mathew, P. (2019). Constructive refoulement. In *Research handbook on international refugee law* (pp. 207-223). Edward Elgar Publishing.

Mediendienst Integration (2025). "Der Hauptweg aus der Ausreisepflicht 5 June 2025, <https://mediendienst-integration.de/news/der-hauptweg-aus-der-ausreisepflicht/>

Mielke, K., Mencütek, Z.S., and Wolf, D. (2024). "Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in Germany. WP2 Country Dossier" in GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10671530

Mielke, K., Vollmer, R., Wolf, D., and Mencütek, Z. S. (2025) "Return Migration Infrastructures in Germany – The case of the federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia. WP3 Country Dossier" GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working paper 2025/12. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15193348.

Negishi, Y. (2024). Constructive Refoulement as Disguised Voluntary Return: The Internalised Externalisation of Migrants. *Netherlands International Law Review*, 71(1), 155-176.

Öztürk N.Ö. (2017). "Geçici Korumanın Uluslararası Koruma Rejimine Uyumu Üzerine Bir İnceleme." *Ankara Üniversitesi Hukuk Fakültesi Dergisi* 66(1): 201-264.

Öztürk N.Ö. (2020). "Irregular Migratory Movements from Turkey to Greek Islands: The Effect of the Readmissions Based on the EU-Turkey Statement over the Rights of the Asylum Seekers." *Journal of the Sea and Maritime Law* 3: 71–166.

Öztürk N.Ö., Öztürk K. B. (2023). *A General Legal Review of Administrative Detention Regulations and Practices in Turkey*. <https://multeci.org.tr/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Annex-22-Eng.-A-GENERAL-LEGAL-REVIEW-OF-ADMINISTRATIVE-DETENTION-REGULATIONS-AND-PRACTICES-IN-TURKEY-3.pdf>

Öztürk N.Ö., and Ovacık G.(2024). "Yabancılar ve Uluslararası Kanununun 10. Yılında Mevzuat ve Mahkeme Kararları Bağlamında Sınır Dışı Uygulamalarının Değerlendirilmesi," In *Türkiye'de Uluslararası Koruma ve Göç*, Ayşe Dicle Ergin and Yiğit Kader (eds.), Onikilevha: 129-172.

Papatzani, E., Kandylis, G., Hatziprokopiou, P., Koutrolidou, P., Psallidaki, T., Varouxi, Ch., Vezyrgianni, K. (2025). WP3: Return Migration Infrastructures. Country Dossier: Greece.

GAPs: Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond. Working Paper: 2025/17. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15705012

PICUM. (2022). Regularisation mechanisms and programmes: Why they matter and how to design them, https://picum.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Regularisation-mechanisms-and-programmes_Why-they-matter-and-how-to-design-them_EN.pdf

PMM. (2021). Irregular migrants received from 4 April 2016 under the 18th March agreement. <https://en.goc.gov.tr/return-statistics>

PMM. (2024). 2024-2028 Stratejik Planı, http://www.sp.gov.tr/upload/xSPStratejikPlan/files/fLdfE+goc_idaresi_24-28_sp.pdf

ProAsyl (2021). The Situation of Afghan Refugees in Turkey, https://www.proasyl.de/wp-content/uploads/PA_Expert-Opinion_The-Situation-of-Afghan-Refugees-in-Turkey.pdf

Rodenhäuser, T. (2023). Pushed to Breaking Point? The Prohibition of ‘Constructive’ or ‘Disguised’ Refoulement under International Law. *International Journal of Refugee Law*, 35(4), 419-440.

Russell, R. and Kuschminder, K. (2022).” Introduction: definitions, typologies and theories of return migration.” In *Handbook of Return Migration*, Russell King and Katie Kuschminder, eds.). Elgar, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781839100055>, <https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/edcoll/9781839100048/9781839100048.00008.xml>

Sahin Mencütek, Z. S. (2022). “The institutionalisation of ‘voluntary’ returns in Turkey.” *Migration and Society*, 5(1), 43-58.

Sahin-Mencutek, Z., Triandafyllidou, A., Barthoma, S, Nimmer, M., Rottmann, S., Öztürk, N. and R. Istaiteyeh (2023). “Framework paper on the concepts and typologies on returns, combined with four conceptual notes” in *Global Migration: Consequences and Responses Vol.1: 78*, Uppsala: Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10021239

Sahin-Mencutek, Z., and Triandafyllidou, A. (2024). “Coerced return: formal policies, informal practices and migrants’ navigation.” *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 51(2), 483–500. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2024.2371209>

Schultz, J. (2020). The end of protection? Cessation and the ‘return turn’ in refugee law, Available at: <https://eumigrationlawblog.eu/the-end-of-protection-cessation-and-the-return-turn-in-refugee-law/>

Stel, N. (2025). ‘The dog that barks doesn’t bite’? Non-performativity in migration diplomacy: EUropean-Lebanese engagement on refugee return to Syria. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2025.2529499>

Tazzioli, M. (2020a). *The Making of Migration: The Biopolitics of Mobility at Europe’s Borders*. SAGE Publishing.

Tazzioli, M. (2020b). Governing migrant mobility through mobility: Containment and dispersal at the internal frontiers of Europe. *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*, 38(1), 3-19.

Torres Chedraui, A. M., Leerkes, A., Ince Beqo, G. and Ambrosini, M. (2024). Legitimate Return and Alternatives to Return, <https://fair-return.org/working-paper-legitimate-return-and-alternatives-to-return/>

Ulusoy O., Yigit-Aksu Ö., Ineli-Ciger M., and Ovacik G. (2025). “Cooperation for Containment: An Analysis of the EU-Türkiye Arrangements in the Field of Migration,” In *Global Asylum Governance and the European Union’s Role*, S. Carrera Nunez, E. Karageorgiou, G. Ovacik, N.F. Tan (eds), pp. 233-255: (E-book): Springer.

UNHCR and EU. (2018). Alternatives to Detention: Definition and Rationale of ATDs, <https://www.onlinelibrary.iihl.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/2018-UNHCR-EU-Alternatives-to-Detention-Module-1.pdf>

Welfens, N. (2023). “Promising victimhood’: contrasting deservingness requirements in refugee resettlement.” *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 49(5), 1103-1124.

About the Authors

Dr. N. Ela Gökalp-Aras is a Senior Researcher at the Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul (SRII), Sweden/Turkey. She is the Principal Investigator (PI) and co-leader of WP2 (Legal and Policy Frameworks of Returns in the EU) of the GAPs Project. She is a postdoctoral researcher on the PHOENIX: Human Mobility, Global Challenges, and Resilience in an Age of Social Stress Project. She has a BA in International Relations (Ankara University), an MSc in Climate Change and Development (University of London, SOAS), and an MSc and a PhD in Sociology (Middle East Technical University). She is one of the editors of the International Journal of Human Mobility (IJHM).

Dr. Neva Övünç Öztürk is a senior researcher at the Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul (SRII). She obtained her LL.B. from Ankara University's Faculty of Law and her LL.M. and PhD from the Institute of Social Sciences at Ankara University. As a Jean Monnet scholar, Dr. Öztürk conducted a significant part of her doctoral studies at Queen Mary, University of London. She has contributed to several projects and training sessions conducted by national and international organisations, and presented papers at international and national conferences on immigration and refugee law. She works as an academic member of the Ankara University Faculty of Law, Department of Private International Law.

Copyright Clause: This work is licensed by the GAPs Consortium under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License, 2020. For details, see <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

GAPs Consortium

Uppsala University (Sweden, Co-Coordinator)
 Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (Germany, Co-Coordinator)
 Stichting Radboud University (Netherlands)
 Özyeğin University (Turkey)
 Hammurabi Human Rights Organisation (Iraq)
 Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul (Sweden/Turkey)
 Hashemite University (Jordan)
 Ethniko Kentro Koinonikon Erevnon (Greece)
 Association Migration Internationale (Morocco)
 Toronto Metropolitan University (Canada)
 University of Nigeria (Nigeria)
 Bilim Organisation for Research and Social Studies (Afghanistan)
 University of Warsaw (Poland)
 Migration Matters EV (Germany)
 University of Sousse (Tunisia)
 SPIA UG (Germany)
 University of Glasgow (UK, Associated Partner)